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Arabian Dates

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Cultivation on Drylands in Tamil Nadu

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Introduction

Tamil Nadu is heavily dependent on monsoon rains, and thereby is prone to droughts when the monsoons fail. Since the state is entirely dependent on rains for recharging its water resources, monsoon failures lead to acute water scarcity and severe drought. Most part of Tamil Nadu falls under Tropical savanna climate and a small portion of the state falls under Humid subtropical climate and climate of the state ranges from dry sub-humid to semi-arid. Therefore, Arabian date palms should be the right choice for our Agriculturists growing crops in water scarce areas. They belong to the phoenix family, which are very common in India and particularly in (South India) Tamil Nadu, Andhra Pradesh, and Karnataka States. In a shift from traditional crops, an increasing number of farmers in Tamil Nadu are taking to cultivating Arabian date palms. Arabian

date palms give the best fruit, and plants are usually imported from Saudi Arabia for cultivation in the State. These are capable of withstanding harsh and drought climatic conditions, erratic rainfall and saline affected regions. These can be grown with minimum maintenance, low expenditure and with nil chemical fertilizer expenses. They do not get attacked by pests and diseases. Animals do not browse these trees. The date fruits have high nutrient value and medicinal uses. Considering the minimum input, the profits are enormous. Arabian dates are cultivated on more than 2,000 acres in the state. Relevant statics indicate that around only 10% of the world product dates are traded. India imports around 40% of dates offered for sale of world market. Though the per head consumption is low in the country, India stands first in importing 4 lakhs tonnes of dates every year.

Climate

Dates need temperature ranging from 30 to 45 degree Celsius and a rainfall of 200 to 250 mm per year for a conducive growth. The sapling is also well-suited for 30-40 degree temperatures. During flowering the temperature should not be less than 15°C, without frost and absence of rain. The Climate of Tamil Nadu is generally humid subtropical climate and features fairly hot temperature over the year except during the monsoon season with little variation in summer and winter temperatures. While April-June is the hottest summer temperature with 40°C. November-February is the coolest winter temperature with 20°C. The average annual rainfall in Tamil Nadu ranges between 25 and 75 inches (945mm) a year. So practically Tamil Nadu climatic condition is suitable for Date Palm cultivation.

Soil

Date Palm Grows in all types of soil. Even grows in Kallar lands. Deep, sandy loam soils ideal for maximum water-holding capacity and good drainage are desirable. Date palm can grow in Alkaline or Saline and Arid deserts soils but in such soils its growth and productivity are greatly reduced. The soil profile should be free from stones of calcium carbonate concretions and hard pan at least up to 2 m depth. Date palm tolerates high soil salinity (PH 8-10). It can survive in soils having 4 % salt concentration, provided the root system does not come in contact with a stratum of soil where the sodicity is more than 1%.

Varieties

More than 1,000 varieties of dates are known to exist. However, only a few of them are commercially cultivated in different countries. The important arabial date varieties cultivated in Tamil Nadu were: Ajiva, Madhumiyani, Shukri, Muscat, Meznaz, Sayer, Zaghloul ; Barri, Zahidi, Khadrawy, Khalas, Hajuva, Kalima, Khadri, Saqee, Sughara (small) Barhee and Afghan Fig.

Propagation

There are two common methods that are used to propagate palm trees, by seed and by using offshoots.

1. Seed Propagation: Seeds were collected from good female cultivars and kept in cloth bags or perforated tin cans and left in the running water of a falaj. One week later, the imbibed seeds were sown in a nursery plot that is especially prepared for this purpose and the seedling then left there for one year. After that, the seedlings were transplanted to their permanent place in the farm. Since 50% of the seedlings will be undesirable males, farmers stopped using this method of propagation long time ago and adopted the vegetative one. This method is still used in few areas to grow palms for pollen production when offshoots are not available.
2. Vegetative Propagation: Almost all the existing orchards are vegetatively propagated by offshoots. The small-sized offshoot is removed from the mother plant with a locally made machete and placed in moist place either in the falaj or under the farm trees to provide shade and allow roots to develop. Arab growers avoided large shoots and the ones that are crowded together and shaded by offshoot trees. Generally, no green leaves are removed from the offshoot until it is cut from the parent palm, as the growth of an offshoot will be proportional to its leaf area. Separation of the offshoots normally carried out in the late summer and fall. After the root develops, the young trees are transplanted to their permanent place.

Planting

The two methods of propagated sapling are differently planted like:

Seed Propagated Palm Tree: This type of sapling planting pit size should be 2 x 2 x 2 feet. Bio-fertilizers like earthworm manure, sheep manure or Farm Yard Manure (FYM) any one of these can

